

An Experiment On Data Structures

Start of Block: Introduction

Intro This experiment is about the use of data structures. The experiment contains 3 programming tasks. You can implement them in any relevant programming language. Note that the goal is not to evaluate your skill, but to characterize the approaches different developers use. The experiment is intended for developers with at least basic programming knowledge.

Participation in the experiment is anonymous and we do **not** collect any identifying information. The results will be used for research purposes only. You may retire at any point (even though we'd be happy if you stay with us until the end). The experiment is expected to take 10-15 minutes. Continuing to the questionnaire indicates agreement to participate in the research.

End of Block: Introduction

Start of Block: Reminder

reminder **Reminder:**

Reminder: The linked list structure contains nodes that are linked to each other. More accurately, the linked list object contains a pointer to its first node object and every node object contains some value and a pointer to the next node object in the list (or to null) Illustration for a linked list:

BT The binary tree structure contains nodes that are also linked to each other. More accurately, the binary tree object contains a pointer to its first node object and every node contains some

value and pointers to additional node objects, designated left and right sons. Illustration of a binary tree:

BST A Binary Search Tree (BST) is a binary tree in which all the nodes follow the below-mentioned properties –

- * The values of all the keys in the left sub-tree are less than the value of its parent (root) node's key.
- * The values of all the keys in the right sub-tree are greater than or equal to the value of its parent (root) node's key.

End of Block: Reminder

Start of Block: Binary Tree

BT Given a binary tree T, Implement a function that finds the number of odd values in it.

End of Block: Binary Tree

Start of Block: FACTORIAL

FACT Given an array with n integers with no duplicate elements, write a function that returns the number of possible permutations of the array elements.

Please write the explicit code.

End of Block: FACTORIAL

Start of Block: Arrays

Arr Given two arrays and their sizes, implement a function that returns true if the arrays are identical, else returns false.

Identical arrays contains the same elements in the same order.

End of Block: Arrays

Start of Block: Linked List

1st Implement a function that receives as input a linked list and returns the number of positive values in it.

End of Block: Linked List

Start of Block: BST1

SEARCHBST Implement a function that gets as input a binary search tree and a value. The function returns true if the value exists in the tree, and false otherwise.

End of Block: BST1

Start of Block: BST2

MAXBST Given a binary search tree T, Implement a function that finds the maximal value in T.

End of Block: BST2

Start of Block: Demographic

Q1 What is your gender?

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - Non-binary / third gender (3)
 - Prefer not to say (4)
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Q2 What is your programming education?

- High School (1)
 - Current BSc student (2)
 - BSc degree (3)
 - MSc student or degree (5)
 - PhD student or degree (7)
 - Self taught, vocational training, army (8)
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Q3 How many years of real programming experience (including army if relevant) do you have?

Q4 What is your profession?

- Profesional developer (1)
- Academic career / student (2)
- Other (3)

End of Block: Demographic
